

**ACUTE UPPER GASTROINTESTINAL
ENDOSCOPIC COMPLICATIONS IN
GENERAL HOSPITALS ENDOSCOPY UNITS
IN
SALAHUDDIN GOVERNORATE, IRAQ
and ABU DHABI ,U.A.E.**

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مسح المضاعفات الحادة الحادثة نتيجة تنظيف أعلى الجهاز الهضمي
في شعبة تنظيف الجهاز الهضمي في مستشفى تكريت العام في تكريت
محافظة صلاح الدين – العراق

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الخلاصة

مسح المضاعفات الحادة الناتجة من عملية تنظيف أعلى الجهاز الهضمي في شعبة ناظور الجهاز الهضمي في مستشفى تكريت العام في تكريت.
خلال خمس سنوات امتدت من 1992 حتى نهاية 1996, تم تنظيف أعلى الجهاز الهضمي ل (2000) مريض في المستشفى المذكور.
المضاعفات كانت عديدة ولكن قليلة الحدوث نسبياً لكل منها.
لقد قسمت المضاعفات كما يلي:
قبل عملية التنظيف = 8 .
أثناء عملية التنظيف = 19 .
بعد عملية التنظيف = 8 .
لم نشاهد مضاعفات مزمنة أو مرضية شديدة أو وفاة نتيجة التنظيف.
كل المضاعفات كانت بسيطة وسريعة الزوال.
تم تحديد نسبة حدوث كل مضاعفة.

Acute Upper Gastrointestinal Endoscopic (UGE) Complications (UGEC) in Tikrit General Hospital (TGH) in IRAQ and Abu Dhabi General Hospitals

Summary:

Acute endoscopic complications in upper gastrointestinal endoscopy unit in TGH in Tikrit, were surveyed over 5 years. Two thousand patients had UGE in TGH in Tikrit. Complications faced were too many .but infrequent for each one. It was possible to classify the complications as follows:

- A: Before the procedure: 8
- B: During the procedure: 19
- C: After the procedure : 8

Either one can be further categorized to

- 1-Hazards to the patients.
- 2-Hazards to the endoscopist and other health personnel.

Chronic complications were not studied; there was neither mortality nor permanent morbidity.

All complications were trivial and self-limiting. Serious complications (angina, abortion, etc.) were not seen. The frequency of each acute complication is determined.

Key words: Endoscopy, complications, gastrointestinal, Tikrit.

Introduction:

Generally fiberoptic endoscopy is a safe procedure. It may be regarded a semi-invasive. For, although the endoscope is advanced down to the duodenum, there is hardly any actual invasion of the intestinal mucosa (except for biopsy). (The risk of upper endoscopy to a patient with a good general health is negligible) (1). (Gastrointestinal endoscopy is almost non-invasive) (2). However complications do occur, some people think that (Relative disadvantages are that endoscopy is invasive, time-consuming, usually needs administration of sedatives and carries a small but definite morbidity and even mortality) (3). (Endoscopy has the disadvantage of higher cost) (4) in comparison with radiology and (Higher patient morbidity and mortality) (4) . (Mortality is 0.001 % for non-therapeutic endoscopy) (4). (The commonest hazard to the patient is erroneous diagnosis) (5), which means erroneous interpretation of the endoscopic findings by an un-experienced endoscopist. The more skillful the operator the less likely the diagnosis will be erroneous. At the same time (Other complications will be kept to the minimum) (5). (Complications are most frequent when the operator is inexperienced) (6). Several large surveys suggest a risk of serious complications during diagnostic UGEC of approximately 1 in 800 and a risk of death of approximately 1 in 5000 (6). The risks are higher in emergency procedure and in the elderly and seriously ill. (6)

Complications include those due to drugs such as local anesthetics (tracheal aspiration, cardiac arrhythmias and sudden death) and diazepam .(5,7) Possible complications are perforation of the esophagus or stomach, inhalations of secretions, cardiac arrhythmias or arrest, and transmission of infection, all these are rare (8). A morbidity of 0.13 % and mortality of 0.004 % have been reported (1, 6, 9). (Serious complications occur in only one patient per thousand examined and death in one per five thousands. Perforation occurs most often in the esophagus⁽¹⁰⁾, {in the stomach or duodenum, insufflations of air may burst a recently sealed perforated ulcer} (10). {Hypoxemia, unrelated to medication, may occur in patients with obstructive airway diseases and this may precipitate arrhythmia} (10). {Serious complication is a risk in emergency endoscopy for bleeding or gastric outlet obstruction. {Transmission of infection, mucosal trauma, instrument impaction in

the esophagus and bleeding are all potential hazards, but are rare} (10). The above mentioned complications were also listed by another endoscopist (11).

The complications resulting from diagnostic procedures are diverse and include both local and systemic reactions (12). For example vasovagal reactions can accompany any procedure and are characterized by nausea, sweating, epigastric distress, hyper salivation, weakness, confusion, bradycardia, blurring of vision, and loss of consciousness (12). (Bacteraemia may occur with many diagnostic procedures but is most common when there is interruption of the normal mucosal barriers of a contaminated site) (12). Trivial complications include sore throat, peripheral thrombophlebitis from diazepam injection and some abdominal discomfort if insufflated air has not been aspirated at the end of the procedure. These are fairly common and can be ameliorated by good endoscopic practice (13). Major complications are rare and the mortality rate is extremely low, when deaths do occur, they are usually due to apnea attacks in the elderly patients who have been given too much sedation, perforation of the esophagus and the colon can also occur, but the frequency of these complications is low and may be decreasing with increased endoscopic skill and improved design of instruments (13). Cross infection from endoscopes has occasionally been reported, Salmonella and Pseudomonas are the commonest organisms involved. Although there is concern about Hepatitis B and C viruses, no convincingly documented case has so far been reported. [Good cleaning schedule should prevent this complication]. (13). {Complications of esophago-gastroduodenoscopy are aspiration, apnea, Mallory Weiss laceration 0.1 %, and esophageal rupture 0.03 %} (12). These complications are, however, rare and the procedure is performed safely in outpatients (12).[out of 24,195 OGDs there were 3 reported complications (one perforation of pharyngeal pouch ,treated conservatively ,one chest pain after over-insufflation and one slow recovery after intravenous sedation ;there was no mortality)(This good safety record is probably attributable to careful case selection and minimal use of intravenous sedation)](14).

The already mentioned complications may accompany diagnostic endoscopy. Probably more serious complications may accompany

therapeutic endoscopy, which is rather a more invasive procedure, for example, injection sclerotherapy of esophageal varices may be accompanied by many complications inherent to the procedure. (Pain was the most constant problem after the injection. It was not related to the site or type of the sclerosing substance, used for injection, but positive relation was encountered in relation to its amount. It was more severe with large dose of injection. (Fever, around 38° C, occurring within the first 24 hours, was noticed in 20 patients after ethanolamine maleate injection. No fever was noticed in the sixteen patients who received hypertonic glucose injection) (15) (Ulcer at the site of injection was seen in fifteen patients, twelve had perivariceal and three had intravariceal injections) (15) (ascites was noticed to get worse after the injection in twelve patients out of thirty two patients who had ascites) (15) (Two peculiar complications were noticed, Mallory Weiss syndrome and acute pancreatitis, with high serum amylase .Both responded well to conservative treatment)(15) (Most of the patients developed mild fever, for the first twenty four hours following the procedure .Two patients developed severe burning retrosternal pain and received narcotic analgesics for its relief)(16),but (none has developed late complications ,such as esophageal rupture,stenosis,ulceration or dysphagia) (16).

Another endoscopist found that (complications of injection sclerotherapy are(17) :

- 1-perforation {rare}
- 2-bleeding
- 3-oesophageal ulceration
- 4-oesophageal stricture
- 5-Adult Reparatory Distress Syndrome
- 6-bronchopleural fistula

[The overall complication rate is 0.1 to 0.2 %, mortality is about 0.03%.Drug related complications are most common and include phlebitis and respiratory depression. Common procedural complications are aspiration, bleeding from biopsy site ,and perforation .Transient bacteremia may occur [8%] but is unassociated with endocarditis](18).

Hemorrhage may occur following polypectomy. (13)

{Complications after diagnostic endoscopy of the upper gastrointestinal [GIT]were related to anesthesia in 2 of 12,841 patients .Diagnostic

endoscopy of upper GIT is safe with a complication rate of less than 1 per 5000 cases .Therapeutic endoscopy increase the risk of complications }(19)

Gangi S et al found that the risk of procedure –related cardiovascular complications, for in-patients undergoing hospital-based GI endoscopy, was 2 to 70 times higher than previously reported .Independent risk factors were A-male gender. B-modified Goldman score. C-The use of propofol.

Goldman score was defined as [arrhythmia ,chest pain or anginal equivalent ,hypotension or myocardial infarction occurring within 24 hours after endoscopy] (20) [complications were more frequent in sedated patients and the most frequent complication in all groups studied was mild desaturation] (21) [most of the adverse events associated with diagnostic endoscopy were attributable to use of medication](22) .[The overall sedation-related morbidity was 0.18%and the mortality rate was 0.0014%] (23)

Patients and Methods

More than four thousand five hundred patients had OGD in endoscopy unit in Tikrit General Hospital in Tikrit city ,the capital of Salahuddeen Governorate ,Iraq ,from the beginning of 1992 till the end of 1999 (i.e. ,over 8 years) and in U.A.E over the period 08/2001 till date .The demographic data of the patients ,the caring physicians ,the operating physicians ,results of endoscopy and the complications were recorded .

In Iraq ,the instrument used was Olympus GIF Q20 for adults and PQ20 for children. The light source was SLE10 Olympus also .A double-chambered vacuum sucker was utilized . The procedure was carried out by the writer and an assistant who fixes the mouth piece .Anesthesia was not used (local or general ,as it was not available) { except in one case ,where endoscopy was carried out on an already anaesthetized and bleeding patient } .Each procedure took an average of 8-15 minutes (including the preparation ,explanation to the patient ,procedure proper, cleansing of the instrument ...etc).Each patient was carefully observed for the vital signs [clinical pulse and mercurial sphygmomanometer] but not SPaO₂ [not available instrument] .

In U.A.E., Abu Dhabi OGDs were carried out in primary care hospitals .The operator [the writer]used video-endoscopes [Fujinon and Olympus] over the period 2/2000 till 02/2010.

Premedication consisted of midazolam intravenously and local xylocaine spray of the pharynx .Occasionally [buscopan 20 mg injection]was utilized if there were a lot secretions or pylorosapsm. The instruments were sterilized by machinery .The patients were monitored for their SPaO₂ and vital signs digitally .

RESULTS

The complications were observed and recorded as such:

1- Just before the procedure, i.e., while explaining to the patient. The impact of explanation on the patient was observed .No. of complications categories was 8.

2- During and immediately after the procedure [during the recovery] No complications were noticed outside the endoscopy room .Nineteen categories were observed.

3- Complications after the procedure : Eight categories were observed.

DISCUSSION

We thought from the early beginning of dividing the complications into pre-, intra- and post-OGD or procedural complications would make them easier to tackle .Kavic and Basson have divided the complications they faced into a-Preprocedural [mainly medication effects and and adverse effects of bowel preparation and b- Procedural [primarily perforation hemorrhage and infections](24).

1-PreProcedural complications :

Bad preoccupation about endoscopy was the most frequent type ,noticed in Iraq. This was due to bad reputation of endoscopy ,resulting from poor OGD practice ,especially in the first year of OGD in our governorate .Poor experience ,including to poor explanation to the patient will hinder cooperation during OGD and hence more complications .On the other hand complications magnify bad preoccupation. The least common complication was syncope, possibly because OGD is minimally invasive .Apprehension and palpitation are linked together and are the squeals of and result in incorporation. Refusal to undergo OGD, just few minutes before the procedure, was rather common, while vomiting at the scene of OGD was unusual and occurred in fragile hypersensitive patients .This is linked to dizziness which may be due to hyperventilation associated with apprehension. Overcrowding, which is rather an administrative matter may magnify already mentioned possibilities .Few cases of nausea and vomiting did occur. The frequency of these complications is getting less with the buildup of experience .

2-IntraProcedural Complications :

Nausea and vomiting are due to direct stimulation of gag reflex by the OGD tube .Belching and abdominal pain are due to air insufflations .Dizziness was reported by few patients, mainly females, probably due to vasovagal stimulation. Hypersalivation was actually due to presence of a foreign body in the mouth ,plus accumulation of saliva in the mouth

resulting from difficulty deglutition during OGD .Hypersalivation and laryngeal irritation by the tube may cause a feeling of suffocation. Nasal obstruction may be due to oropharyngeal and oronasal secretions trickling down in the nasal cavity due to head tilt. Severe gag reflex and suffocation may induce irritability, leading the patient to catch the tube and try self-extubation with possible slipping of mouth piece .However tube biting did not occur . We used to warn the patient of the danger of tube biting.

Extubating as such did happen but it was harmless .Many patients expressed palpitation during and after the procedure ,but this was not confirmed objectively, in Iraq and UAE, as there was no Realtime ECG display .The palpitation is assumed to be due to sinus tachycardia ,which normally accompanies the procedure ,especially at the earlier few minutes .This was evident in digital manometer used in UAE. Cough was induced by direct stimulation of cough receptors in the larynx and trachea ,but it was harmless .Inadvertent tracheal intubation was followed by immediate extubation and correction of the tube pathway. Resistance to introduction of the tube ,in the oral cavity ,and coiling was noticed several times .It was caused by the tongue pushing the tube outwards .This was handled by further explanation to the patient and sometimes the left index finger was pushed towards the posterior tongue to assist the progress of the tube .No operator finger biting occurred as the mouth piece was still in situ .Coiling of the tube inside the oral cavity and or the stomach necessitated extubation and re-introduction of the tube .Mild traumatic bleeding occurred in the mouth and stomach. Two cases of dentures slipping were recorded, but were not inhaled .Dentures should have been removed before intubation, which was carried out in later OGDs.This complication was noticed earlier in Iraq but not later and not in UAE. During endoscopy transient reductions in SpaO₂ were noticed especially in the elderly .This was corrected by increasing O₂ flow rate and proper posturing of the patients .As said earlier oximetry was not used in Iraq in the early 1990 because the oximeter was not available ,but even in Europe the frequency of using the oximeter was low at that time [Oximetry monitoring was used in more than 95% of examinations{2003}{compared with 2.5 %in 1990}} (23).This did not have harmful long-term effects on the patients health or cognition.

However [mild desaturation occurs in 27.35 % of patients ,being more severe in therapeutic procedures] as noticed by Ciriza upon studying sedation effect in upper GIT endoscopy .(25) Rex DK et al noticed five episodes of oxygen desaturation ,out of 2222 procedures, to less than 85% and four of these required one minute of mask ventilation .His team suggested that continuous transcutaneous CO2 monitoring or capnography will enhance the safety of propofol .(26).[most complications are related to sedation] (27). Quadri A et al reported a [30% rate of O2 desaturation to <90% and 20% rate of BP readings of <90/60 mmHg following propofol administration by an anesthesiologist] (28) .But Kulling and Inanven,from Switzerland had only 3.7 % of his their patients going to a saturation of <90 % and 7.3 % of their patients became hypotensive with a mean BP of <50 mmHg (29).

[EGD (OGD)is a safe procedure .Perhaps the most common problem associated with the technique arises from preparatory sedation and analgesia] (30). In our series perforation did not occur, but one case of post-OGD bronchopneumonia occurred due to inhalation of stomach contents following a severe bout of vomiting .

Bleeding and perforation were the main complications faced by H Ono et al.(31)

3-PostProcedural Complications

Nausea, vomiting, dizziness, syncope, abdominal pain, palpitation, and retching have the same bases for complications already mentioned. The frequency and percentage of each complication are stated in the table 3, where we can guess that abdominal pain and sore throat were the most frequent. Sore throat is probably caused by direct irritation of the pharynx by the tube. Few cases of stool positive for occult blood were recorded, mostly due to traumatic bleeding. Biopsies for H.pylori were not available in Iraq but are available in UAE. One case of xylocaine allergy was encountered .The patient presented with mild soreness of the throat .His uvula was enlarged and dangling down on the tongue. He was relieved with local steroid spray .To our knowledge this is the first case of such complication to be reported. One case of gastric over-insufflation was encountered in UAE .The patient developed a lot of belching and got rid of air without after ill-effects

[see reference 14 in the discussion]

Over 15 years of work, major complications occasionally mentioned in the literature were not encountered. These include: Sepsis , severe bleeding , drug induced thrombophlebitis, angina pectoris, myocardial infarction, , gastric rupture, abortion, precipitation of asthmatic attack, endoscope sticking inside the stomach or duodenum, respiratory arrest, cardiac arrest, esophageal perforation, surgical emphysema, and incontinence.

One case of pulmonary aspiration occurred as noticed earlier . [respiratory depression and aspiration may occur during the procedure](30). Infection control issues during gastrointestinal endoscopy ,which are becoming increasingly important ,can generally be divided into three major areas:

1-infectious complications resulting from the patient own microbial flora (autologous) .

2-infections transmitted from patient to patient by the endoscope .(exogenous)and

3-infections transmitted between the patient and health care provider .

[The frequency of post procedure bacteraemia ranges from 0.5% for flexible sigmoidoscopy to 2.2 % for colonoscopy ,to 4.2 % OGD, 8.9 % for variceal ligation, 11% for ERCP ...etc] (32) but [Although post procedure bacteremia is not uncommon, it seldom results in infectious complications](32). Standard infection control recommendations will help prevent inter-patients infections and patients-staff infections ,which are basically rare .

Complications during special situations like:

a- Pregnancy were not encountered .Actually pregnant ladies were not offered OGD until after delivery .Several complications were seen in other series (33)

b- In children following hematopoietic stem cell transplantation were not encountered as well..Khan has noticed a complication rate of 4.2% during OGDs in his series .He noticed that thrombocytopenia had a significant association with intestinal bleeding in lower GIT endoscopies .(34)

Mamula et al ,in their retrospective review on safety and efficacy of fentanyl and midazolam for upper and lower GIT endoscopy in children ,noticed a 20% frequency of side effects including

bradycardia (0.9 %) ,agitation(1.7 %) ,skin reaction(3.4%),vomiting (6.4%) and mild (2.6%) and moderate hypoxemia (11.2%).Yet they concluded that conscious sedation in this age group is safe and efficacious . (35)

c- The extremely elderly patients :Generally OGD was as safe as it was in other age groups .This was also the conclusion of Clarke GA in his series [Age alone should not influence decisions relating to its utilization (ie,OGD)](36).

d- End-stage renal and liver diseases patients are likely to require endoscopy for many reasons ,some inherent to the illness itself [esophageal varices] and others due to development of GORD or PUD which complicate these long term illnesses .These patients constituted a minority in our series ,but every precaution was considered to minimize the risk of serious adverse effects . Basically **a-**The preparation of blood and blood products and **b-** The preparation of operative theatre for emergency surgery were considered .(37)

e- Patients with heart failure or preexisting heart diseases were not endoscoped .However it is notable that there is an increase in heart rate and the risk of arrhythmia ,ST segment changes during endoscopy .Usually the heart rate and systolic blood pressure and rate –blood pressure product tend to increase after the endoscope was inserted into the esophagus ,but thereafter all these parameters tend to decrease in both sedated and non-sedated patients .(38) .However there was a reduction in oxygen saturation in the sedated group but this did not reach statistical significance .Clearly this fact should be seriously considered upon endoscopic a patient with pre-existing heart disease .

Sedation may improve patient tolerance by reducing anxiety and discomfort .

f- Patients with bleeding tendencies were not endoscoped ...Emergency OGD in these patients carries a high morbidity rate [The patient with coagulation disorders is more likely to experience a retropharyngeal hematoma or other bleeding complication.](18).It is preferable to have endoscopy carried out for these patients in tertiary care centers .

Two further important aspects of complications are :

1-Avoidable versus Unavoidable complications :

Denis et al noticed a rate of 0.7 % of complications ,70% of these occurred during therapeutic procedures .Thirteen percent were considered avoidable and 24 % were probably avoidable(39) .In our series we found that % were avoidable and the rest were unavoidable [see table 5]

2-Whose fault is it when a complication does occur ? Denis et al found that 34% of the complications were due to an error :22 attributed to endoscopist ,4 to the nurses and 1 to the material (39) .Our figures showed that % of the complications were to endoscopist .

How to avoid complications

- a- Training of endoscopists ,nurses and auxiliary staff .
- b- Strict adherence to endoscopy protocols
- c- Strict adherence to drugs protocols .
- d- Careful preprocedural checking of the patients .
- e- Careful selection of the patient .
- f- Thorough explanation of the procedure to the patient .This will help gain the trust of the patient and hence minimize complications .
- g- Careful selection of the procedure and its indication .
- h- Careful postprocedural monitoring of the patient .
- i- Strict adherence to postprocedural advices [i.e. no driving after the procedure].
- j- Proper management of clerking .

In general ...strict implementation of existing guidelines in warranted.

(7)

CONCLUSIONS

- 1- Complications encountered were generally mild and self-limiting, and mostly related to sedation and having a foreign body introduced into the GIT cavity..
- 2- The more skillful the operator, the less the complications are.
- 3- There is hardly any mortality and the morbidity is negligible.
- 4- Hazards to the operator himself and infectious complications are likely but remote.
- 5- Strict implementation of guidelines governing GIT endoscopy will help prevent the morbidity.
- 6- Patients with special situations ,who require endoscopy are better taken care of in tertiary care centers .

Table No. 1
Patients Demographic data

Age Ranges	M	% Out of 4300	F	% Out of 4300	Total F+M	% out of 4300
1 15-20	277	6.45	161	3.75	438	10.2
2 21-30	785	18.25	436	10.15	1221	28.4
3 31-40	871	20.25	447	10.4	1318	30.65
4 41-50	591	13.75	355	8.25	946	22
5 51-60	157	3.65	45	1.05	202	4.7
6 >60	135	3.15	39	0.9	174	4.05
7 total	2816	65.5	1483	34.5	4299	100

Table No. 2
complications before the endoscopy

	Entity	M	% Out of 4300	F	% Out of 4300	Total	% of each entity out of 4300
1	dizziness	22	0.5	43	1	65	1.5
2	palpitation	172	4	258	6	430	10
3	apprehension	77	1.8	387	9	464	10.8
4	refusal	26	0.6	151	3.5	176	4.1
5	nausea	17	0.4	47	1.1	64	1.5
6	vomiting	15	0.35	24	0.55	39	0.9
7	bad preoccupation	323	7.5	346	8.05	669	15.55
8	syncope	2	0.05	4	0.1	6	0.15

complications before endoscopy

Table No. 3
complications during endoscopy

	Entity	M	% Out of 4300	F	% Out of 4300	Total	% of each entity out of 4300
1	nausea[gag]	864	20.1	1118	26	1982	46.1
2	vomiting	688	16	860	20	1548	36
3	belching	236	5.5	279	6.5	515	12
4	dizziness	75	1.75	151	2.75	226	4.5
5	suffocation	75	1.75	54	1.25	129	3
6	nasal obstruction	79	1.85	50	1.15	129	3
7	abdominal pain	453	10.55	387	9	840	19.55
8	hypersalivation	247	5.75	419	9.75	666	15.5
9	slipping of mouth piece	15	0.35	6	0.15	21	0.5
10	irritability	290	6.75	255	5.95	545	12.7
11	extubation by the patient	96	2.25	163	3.8	259	6.05
12	cough	252	5.85	120	2.8	372	8.65
13	oral trauma	236	5.25	238	5.55	474	10.8
14	resistance to incubation	49	1.15	69	1.6	118	2.75
15	coiling inside the mouth	17	0.4	13	0.3	30	0.7
16	coiling inside the stomach	77	1.8	77	1.8	154	3.6
17	slipping of dentures	2	0.05	2	0.05	4	0.1
18	palpitation	307	7.15	217	5.05	524	12.2
19	tracheal incubation	4	0.1	6	0.15	10	0.25
20	SpaO2 changes	255	5.9	245	5.7	500	11.6
21	Bronchopneumonia	1	-	0	-	1	-

Complications during endoscopy

Table No.4 complications after endoscopy

	Entity	M	% Out of 4300	F	% Out of 4300	Total	% of each entity out of 4300
1	nausea[gag]	69	1.6	96	96.75	165	3.85
2	vomiting	28	0.65	43	43	71	1.65
3	dizziness	58	1.35	79	1.85	137	3.2
4	syncope	2	0.05	2	0.05	4	0.1
5	abdominal pain	279	6.5	412	9.6	681	16.1
6	palpitation	21	0.5	17	0.4	38	0.9
7	retching	32	0.75	32	0.75	64	1.5
8	sore throat	204	4.75	120	2.8	324	7.55

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